

Electrically-assisted cyclic torsion of 5083 aluminium alloy

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Abstract. The low formability of aluminum alloys at room temperature is their main disadvantage. Many studies have shown that the application of current pulses to metal alloys during their forming results in an increase in their formability. However, these studies are mainly limited to uniaxial tensile or compression tests. The effect of current pulses on the properties of metal alloys in cyclic torsion tests has not yet been determined. These studies have shown that the application of current pulses during the cyclic torsion process of 5083 aluminum alloy results in an improvement of its plasticity. The main factor responsible for the observed changes is recovery. The application of current pulses is justified in forming processes with different strain states.

Introduction

High specific strength is the main advantage of aluminium alloys, the use of which in the automotive industry results in a reduction in the weight of vehicles and therefore the amount of exhaust gases produced [1]. Unfortunately, the formability of aluminum alloys is low at ambient temperature [2]. Increasing the formability of aluminum alloys is possible, for example, through warm and hot forming [3]. However, these processes are energy-intensive and also have their disadvantages, for example, in the form of reduced lubrication efficiency [4].

The formability of aluminum alloys can also be improved by the electrically-assisted (EA) forming process [5]. In this process, current pulses are applied during the forming of metal alloys. As a result, there is a short-term increase in the material's temperature, repeated cyclically. Many studies have shown that the application of current pulses can significantly improve the plasticity of formed metals. Roh et al. [6] showed that the elongation of 5052-H32 aluminum alloy can be increased to 275% of the initial value when current pulses are applied in the tensile test. Hong et al. [7] observed an increase in displacement and a decrease in force during the compression of 6061-T6 aluminum alloy with the application of current pulses. The positive effect of current pulses was also observed in the case of EA drawing [8] or rolling [9] processes. In both cases, a decrease in the process force and greater plasticity of the material were observed. The observed changes in material properties cannot be explained solely by Joule heating (and thus the increase in material temperature) accompanying the application of current pulses [10]. Therefore, several mechanisms have been proposed to explain the observed changes. Among them, the following can be distinguished: localized Joule heating (thermal component) [11], electron-defect interaction [12,13] or charge imbalance at defects (the last two athermal component) [14]. However, which of these mechanisms plays which role is still debated.

EA forming is well studied for many materials in the uniaxial tensile test. However, the analysis of this phenomenon in processes with more complicated strain state is still missing. Therefore, in this study, for the first time, the influence of current pulses on the mechanical properties and microstructure of 5083 aluminum alloy in the cyclic torsion process was assessed.

Material and Methods

The tested material was delivered in the form of round bars with a diameter of 20 mm made of 5083-H112 aluminium alloy. Samples with a gauge length of 10 mm and a diameter of 5 mm were prepared along the extrusion direction (ED) from the material as delivered. A special-constructed testing machine was used to perform the cyclic torsion process. The cyclic torsion process was carried out in such a way that the sample was initially twisted through an angle of 18° (α - amplitude) and then alternately twisted through an angle of 36° (2α) until fracture (Fig. 1). Shear strains correspond to the angles of 18 and 36° are 0.0785 and 0.157 , respectively. The α angle was experimentally selected in such a way that visible plastic deformation occurred in the material (visible on the stress-strain curve). The tests were carried out for a strain rate of 0.1 s^{-1} . Each test for the given parameters was repeated three times.

EA cyclic torsion tests were carried out by applying a pulsed electric current (current pulses). Current pulses were delivered to the material by a self-constructed current pulse generator operating at a nominal voltage of 2.52 V . The current pulse generator was connected to the sample by wires terminated with electrodes attached to it beyond the gauge length of the sample. Current pulses of duration (d) 500 ms were applied to the sample with different time interval called period (p). Two pulse period values were used in the studies: 20 s and 30 s . During one test, the value of p was constant. The first current pulse was applied to the sample after time p . The current generated by the applied current pulses was measured using a Rogowski coil and displayed by an oscilloscope. The nominal current density was 170 A/mm^2 . During the cyclic torsion test, the sample temperature was continuously measured using a FLIR T840 thermal imaging camera. The surface of the sample was painted with black paint to avoid surface reflectivity during temperature measurement.

A VEGA3 TESCAN scanning electron microscope operating at 20 kV and equipped with an Electron Backscattered Diffraction (EBSD) detector was used to observe the microstructure of the selected process samples. AZtec software (OXFORD) was used to analyze the microstructure using the EBSD method. The applied step size was $0.5 \mu\text{m}$. The samples before analysis were mechanically ground and then electrochemically polished with a Lectropol-5 electrolytic polisher using STRUERS A2 reagent at a voltage of 24 V . Vickers hardness measurements were performed using a LECO LM100AT hardness tester under a load of 0.1 kg .

Figure 1 – Diagram of the cyclic torsion process in the cross-section, where M is the torque

Results and Discussion

The representative stress-strain curve of 5083-H112 aluminium alloy sample without applying a current is shown in Fig. 2a. As can be seen in the enlarged fragment of the curve, twisting the sample by an angle α results in the occurrence of plastic deformations. After reaching the final deflection of the sample, a local stress maximum is observed. Then (for the next 18°) the stress drops to zero and the curve regresses along the strain axis parallel to the previous elastic range of the sample. Thanks to this, despite repeated loading and unloading of the sample, it was possible to determine the total strain value. For the next 18° the sample is twisted in the opposite direction to the initial orientation, which results in negative stress values. However, the stress values on both sides of the axis have the same absolute values.

Figs. 2b and 2c show the stress-strain curves of 5083-H112 aluminium alloy samples with a current application for a pulse period of 30 and 20 s, respectively. The application of current pulses resulted in an average increase in the total strain value of 42 and 22% for samples with a pulse period of 30 and 20 s, respectively. It can be seen that the application of a current pulse resulted in a temporary decrease in the stress on the stress-strain curve. This decrease was accompanied by an increase in the sample temperature to values exceeding even 300°C (Fig. 3a and b). Nevertheless, the average temperature values of the profiles shown in Fig. 3a and b are 45.9°C and 57.1°C , respectively.

Figure 2 – Stress-strain curves of 5083-H112 aluminium alloy samples a) without applying a current and with b) and c) a current application

During the test conducted at room temperature (RT), the stress increased for most of its duration, reaching a constant value in the rest of it. Meanwhile, during EA torsion

tests with current parameters of 500 ms/30 s, the stress had an identical course between individual cycles (except for the first one), reaching lower values than for the test at RT conditions (Fig. 4a). However, for the 500 ms/20 s current parameters (Fig. 4b), the stress curve between individual cycles showed a slight decrease over time. The temperature drop between subsequent current pulses is related to the discharge of the current pulse generator (and its battery) and therefore the application of current pulses with a lower current.

Figure 3 – The corresponding temperature profiles a) and b) of the curves shown in Figs. 2b and 2c, respectively

Figure 4 – Superposition of stress-strain curves of 5083-H112 aluminium alloy samples with and without applying a current.

In order to analyze the effect of current pulses on the microstructure of the tested alloy in the cyclic torsion test, additional tests were performed. The EA cyclic torsion test was additionally performed for current parameters of 500 ms/30 s. After application of the second current pulse, the test was immediately stopped, and a specimen for microstructure examination was cut from its center, along the gauge length of the sample. The same test was repeated, but without the application of current pulses, and stopped after exactly the same duration of cyclic torsion.

Fig. 5a and b present the Inverse Pole Figure (IPF) maps of the non-EA and EA 5083-H112 aluminium alloy specimens, respectively. The typical elongated grains, divided by Low Angles Grain Boundaries (LAGB), seen in Figures 5a and b are the result of the hot extrusion manufacturing process for this alloy. The initial Hit Rate value for non-EA specimen was 68.86% while for EA specimen it was 80.32%. Much more indexed points for the EA specimen can be observed especially near the edge of the sample, which is located in the lower part of Fig. 5. The Grain Orientation Spread (GOS) maps, for the same specimens as in Fig. 5, are shown in Fig. 6.

Using GOS maps, it is possible to verify whether the examined microstructure has undergone the recrystallization process.

Figure 5 – IPF maps of 5083-H112 aluminium alloy specimen obtained under: a) non-pulsed and b) pulsed conditions

Figure 6 – GOS maps of 5083-H112 aluminium alloy specimen obtained under: a) non-pulsed and b) pulsed conditions

For this purpose, the grains should be assigned a GOS parameter value of no more than 1.5°. Microstructure analysis for the EA specimen does not indicate the presence of grains after the recrystallization process as a result of current pulse application. However, this analysis is hindered by the large number of LAGB present in the material in the delivery state.

Studies have shown that the plasticity (in the form of the total strain value) of the 5083-H112 aluminium alloy can be increased by more than 40% (Fig. 4). Plasticity was increased in the material formed with the application of current pulses. In order to obtain such an increase in plasticity in a conventional manner, it is necessary to use warm forming at a temperature of approximately 200-250 °C. However, in this case the increase in strain was obtained for an average

temperature value less than 60 °C. Although the temperature course was variable over time (Fig. 3), the low average temperature value indicates low energy consumption of the process. Based on simple energy calculations of the current process, it can be concluded that the energy consumed in the EAF process is at least an order of magnitude lower than for conventional furnace heating for a batch of several dozen samples. Therefore, this EAF process is much more economical than conventional heating of the material in the furnace.

Microstructure analysis (Figs. 5 and 6) did not reveal any effects of dynamic recrystallization processes that could be responsible for the observed changes in the material's plasticity. It is likely that for such a short time of the annealing process the temperature reached was too low to cause the material to recrystallize [15]. It is possible that this process has started, but it would be necessary to analyze the microstructure using higher magnifications, e.g. transmission electron microscopy, to assess this phenomenon. Therefore, the dynamic recovery process was the main factor responsible for the observed changes in the mechanical properties of the tested aluminum alloy [16]. This is confirmed by, among others, the recorded value of the Hit Rate coefficient, which indicates the percentage of indexed measurement points. The lower value of Hit Rate (non-EA forming) is caused by the deformation of the material structure and thus the difficulty (or impossibility) of performing diffraction in a given area, which results in the lack of indexing of this area. However, in the case of EA forming, the increase in temperature causes the dynamic healing to begin, which is responsible for the reconstruction of the crystal structure. The partially rebuilt structure results in the EA-formed material having a Hit Rate value that is almost 12 percentage points higher. The above is also confirmed by hardness measurements (Fig. 7). These measurements were performed for the same samples for which microstructure studies were conducted. The variable d on the abscissa axis is the distance from the edge of the sample. It is clearly seen that regardless of the distance from the sample edge, the hardness is about 10 HV0.1 higher for the non-EA than for the EA samples. The higher hardnesses observed closer to the edge of the sample are the result of greater structural deformations in this area, which increase with distance from the sample axis.

Figure 7 – Hardness profiles of 5083-H112 aluminium alloy specimens with and without applying a current.

It was confirmed that the pulse period has a visible effect on the mechanical properties of aluminum alloys in the EA cyclic torsion test (Fig. 2). The average increase in strain for the 30 s pulse period was almost twice as large as for 20 s. Analysis of the temperature profiles for both parameters helps to explain these differences. For large strains, higher temperature values occurred in tests with a pulse period of 30 s. Moreover, the periods between pulses were longer, therefore a larger number of structure defects, mainly dislocations, accumulated before application of the next current pulse. Both of these factors, i.e. higher temperature and more dislocations, result in a greater intensity of the dynamic recovery process. Thanks to this, it was possible to obtain a greater

strains for the 30 s pulse period. The pulse period also had an effect on the stress value. It was lower for the 20 s period. In this case, temperature also played a key role, because it causes a softening of the material. Such a high frequency of application of current pulses resulted in a higher average temperature of the sample during the entire test. The next current pulse was applied before the material had time to return to the stress before the previous one was applied.

Summary

The effect of current pulses on the mechanical properties and microstructure of 5083 aluminum alloy in the cyclic torsion test was presented in this paper. The studies showed that it is possible to increase the strain in the EA cyclic torsion test by more than 40% compared to the non-EA test. However, the magnitude of the strain increase depends on the pulse period. Microstructure analysis and hardness measurements showed that the dynamic recovery process was the main factor responsible for the increase in the plasticity of the material. The obtained results suggest that current pulses can be successfully used in processes with different deformation states. The average process temperature of less than 60 °C indicates that this process is more economical than conventional warm forming.

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Author Contributions

Daniel Dobras: Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Project Administration, Visualization, Writing-Original Draft; Karol Jaśkiewicz: Methodology, Investigation, Writing-Review and Editing; Maciej Zwierzchowski: Investigation, Validation, Writing-Review and Editing

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